

The HuT

The HuT innovative nexus modelling activities – lessons learned

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3. Introduction

This Deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the modelling activities carried out across the ten Demonstrators (DEMs) of The HuT project within the framework of Task 4.3. Within this context, modelling is conceptualized as the interpretative bridge that transforms raw environmental data into actionable knowledge, encompassing the simulation of physical hazards, the assessment of dynamic exposure, and the characterization of socio-economic vulnerability. These activities range from high-resolution meteorological and climate forecasting to the development of advanced algorithms for impact prediction. Regardless of the specific computational or statistical approach adopted, modelling activities are consistently framed as decision-support tools for Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA). They are systematically linked to the operational needs of the demonstrators. Modelling does not represent a purely theoretical exercise, but rather a framework where environmental observations are effectively integrated into governance and community engagement. In this sense, the value of a model is assessed not only by its numerical accuracy or computational efficiency, but by its capacity to reduce uncertainty and provide a robust evidence base for the multi-hazard risk management strategies that the project seeks to advance.

For each DEM, a brief introduction to the case study is provided, followed by a description of the modelling activities conducted. The main modelling activities are identified and discussed in terms of their relevance within the Nexus framework, their innovative character, and their potential for amplification. Each section concludes with the lessons learned and a concise summary of the main outcomes. It should be noted that not all DEMs have conducted activities that fall directly within the scope of modelling as defined here. The decision to develop, refine, or simply adopt specific modelling frameworks was dictated by the existing technical baseline, the complexity of the local hazard-risk interactions, and the specific requirements for decision support in each area.

4. Lessons learned from DEMs

4.1. DEM1 Valencia [Spain]

4.1.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

The modelling activities conducted in the Valencia Demonstrator (DEM1) are centered on the multi-dimensional characterization of extreme climate events, specifically targeting heatwaves, droughts, and the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect. By integrating advanced climate simulations, high-resolution satellite analytics, and operational forecasting tools, the DEM provides a comprehensive assessment of climate risks. This analytical framework is designed to evaluate the precise impacts of these hazards on the urban environment and on the most vulnerable populations.

The technical implementation is structured across three primary lines of work:

- **Projection and Characterization of Heatwaves:** To evaluate temporal trends and future climate trajectories, an ensemble of five global climate models (GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1.2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, and UKESM1-0-LL) was utilized under three distinct emission scenarios (SSP126, SSP370, and SSP585). Heatwaves were operationalized using a high-resolution historical baseline, defining events as at least three consecutive days exceeding the 90th percentile of maximum daily temperatures. By analyzing indicators such as intensity, amplitude, and risk levels, this modelling effort demonstrates that climate change is an active, present-day phenomenon already reshaping urban health and living conditions.
- **Seasonal Drought Predictive Analytics using WATER4CAST** (<https://water4cast.webs.upv.es/en/home/>): This line of work addresses the Júcar River Basin's vulnerability to water scarcity through the development of the WATER4CAST platform. The system synthesizes seasonal climate forecasts from four premier European systems (ECMWF-SEAS5, Météo-France System 8, DWD-GCFS2.1, and CMCC-SPSv3.5) available via the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S). These inputs are merged with ERA5 reanalysis data and refined through AI-based post-processing techniques. The resulting probabilistic forecasts provide reliable projections of key drought indices (SPI and SPEI) across multiple temporal scales—from sub-seasonal to seasonal—enabling proactive decision-making in water resource management, agriculture, and environmental protection.
- **Urban Heat Island Modelling:** Utilizing Landsat 9 satellite imagery, the DEM produced high-resolution (30 m) Land Surface Temperature (LST) models to dissect the spatial dynamics of the UHI effect. This physical modelling was coupled with socio-demographic data and land-use classifications to identify the intersection between thermal hot spots and sensitive urban spaces. Through the application of statistical methods such as ANCOVA, the team quantified the direct influence of urban morphology and land cover on temperature distribution. This ensures that mitigation strategies are not only scientifically grounded but also socially targeted.

Beyond these pillars, exploratory modelling was initiated regarding tropical nights, heat-related mortality thresholds, and Local Climate Zones (LCZ), establishing a robust foundation for future scalability. Together, these activities have transitioned from theoretical research into operational tools and datasets, directly contributing to Valencia's climate risk assessment and the strategic advancement of urban resilience.

Figure 1: Framework representing the three main lines of work.

4.1.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

The flagship activity of the Valencia Demonstrator (DEM1) is focused on an integrative modelling framework that evaluates the compounding risks of urban heat and prolonged drought. This approach seeks to understand both the temporal evolution of these hazards through long-term climate projections and their spatial manifestation within the urban environment. By combining medium-scale climate models with high-resolution satellite observations, the project provides a multi-scale analysis of heat risks, identifying how long-term trends translate into specific urban variabilities and thermal hotspots. The relevance of this activity is related to the critical nature of heatwaves and droughts within the Mediterranean, where impacts are often amplified by the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect and socio-economic vulnerability. Traditionally, drought monitoring has been a reactive process, but the transition to seasonal forecasting allows for proactive decision-making several months in advance. The innovation of this effort is further defined by the hybridization of physical variables—such as land cover and 30-meter resolution Land Surface Temperature (LST) data—with granular social vulnerability metrics. By applying statistical methods like ANCOVA, the team has moved beyond descriptive mapping to quantify exactly how urban morphology influences temperature, while a multi-model ensemble approach utilizing AI-based post-processing ensures that drought forecasts are both robust and calibrated against local historical distributions.

This integrated modelling serves as a primary operational junction for the Nexus, establishing a functional link between urban systems, social equity, and environmental governance. It connects city morphology to thermal behavior, providing the necessary evidence for targeted urban planning and adaptation strategies. Simultaneously, the explicit focus on vulnerable populations ensures that disaster risk reduction is socially grounded. This vision is further strengthened by the integration of heat analysis with water management through the WATER4CAST platform, which supports the Júcar River Basin Agency in balancing environmental flows with human and agricultural demands. By treating heat and drought as a single interconnected challenge, DEM1 advances the understanding of climate extremes within the broader water-energy-environment nexus.

4.1.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

The implementation of these activities followed a structured workflow, beginning with the collection of ERA5 reanalysis and Landsat 9 imagery. Heatwaves were characterized based on percentile thresholds to calculate indicators of duration and intensity, which were then compared across various climate scenarios. This physical data was then merged with socio-demographic datasets to perform spatial analyses of hot and cold spots. Crucially, the local team moved beyond research by developing an operational, web-based implementation for drought forecasting. This platform now provides water managers in the Júcar River Basin with probabilistic projections of SPI and SPEI indices, updated monthly to support early warning systems and day-to-day management operations.

The modelling framework developed in DEM1 has a strong potential for amplification and transferability to other geographical contexts. A primary strength of the methodology lies in its reliance on publicly available climate and satellite data, such as the Copernicus C3S datasets and Landsat imagery. This ensures that the approach is replicable in any urban area or river basin where these resources are accessible. Furthermore, the framework is not limited to heatwaves and meteorological droughts; it is inherently adaptable to multiple climate hazards, including tropical nights and minimum temperature extremes. In particular, the drought forecasting component's use of AI post-processing on open-access data makes it relatively straightforward to adapt to different river basins, provided local teams can perform the necessary calibration against regional historical records.

Despite these advantages, several technical and operational constraints must be considered when scaling or replicating the approach. A significant challenge is the inherent uncertainty associated with climate models and future emission scenarios, which requires careful interpretation. Operationally, there is a distinct spatial mismatch between the high-resolution physical data—where temperature readings are obtained at 30 or 100-meter scales—and the socio-demographic information, which is often only available at the much broader census scale. This resolution gap introduces complexity in characterizing population exposure at municipal level. Furthermore, the limited density of ground-based weather stations complicates the validation of temperature retrievals across different Local Climate Zones (LCZs). For drought forecasting, transferability is also influenced by basin-specific factors such as topography and teleconnections, which necessitate localized tuning to maintain forecast skill.

Concerning the implementation, the approach could be further refined or expanded in several areas. While the current framework provides a solid foundation, a deeper integration of Local Climate Zones would significantly improve urban classification and thermal precision. Future iterations should aim to complete the analysis of tropical nights and minimum temperature extremes, alongside the inclusion of neighborhood-scale heat mortality thresholds to better quantify health risks. Technically, the modelling of 2-meter air temperature could be improved to bridge the gap between surface and ambient temperature. Additionally, expanding the drought component to

include hydrological and agricultural indices would provide a more comprehensive risk profile. Finally, enhancing the communication of probabilistic forecasts within the WATER4CAST platform would help non-technical stakeholders better interpret uncertainty, ensuring that these advanced modelling outputs are as actionable as possible for all users.

4.1.4. Take-home messages

The activities carried out in DEM1 demonstrate that understanding urban heat requires a multi-scale approach that integrates long-term climate projections with high-resolution socio-environmental analysis. A primary takeaway is that climate change is no longer a distant projection but a present reality, with heatwaves becoming more frequent, intense, and prolonged. These thermal extremes are increasingly occurring alongside persistent droughts, making integrated tools like the WATER4CAST platform essential for transforming reactive water management into a proactive, forecast-informed system capable of protecting agriculture and urban resources.

Analysis at the local scale further reveals that urban heat is not a uniform phenomenon determined by proximity to the city center, but is instead strongly dictated by land use, surface materials, and vegetation cover. This spatial heterogeneity results in a clear "thermal inequality", as vulnerable populations are systematically exposed to higher temperatures. Ultimately, the work in Valencia proves that by merging climate modelling with granular spatial and demographic data, it is possible to design adaptation strategies that are both scientifically robust and socially equitable, providing a vital roadmap for enhancing resilience in Mediterranean environments.

4.2. DEM2 Val d'Aran Region [Spain]

4.2.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

The modelling activities in the Val d'Aran Demonstrator (DEM2) focused on the development and operationalization of a comprehensive Multi-Hazard Early Warning System (MHEWS) specifically tailored for high-mountain, snow-dominated environments. The core modelling framework is SCLAM (Snow-CREST-Landslide Modelling), a coupled system that integrates the distributed hydrological model CREST with slope stability analysis. This configuration allows for the simultaneous forecasting of flood and landslide hazards, established through discharge return period thresholds and the quantification of unstable areas. The framework underwent rigorous calibration and validation against major historical events, notably the 2013 flood, where the model demonstrated high precision in replicating observed discharge data.

A key innovation is the implementation of ensemble modelling techniques to enhance landslide prediction accuracy. By utilizing a hybrid methodology that compares Random Forest machine learning with physically-based slope stability models, the system leverages both data-driven patterns and process-based physical laws. After evaluating multiple weather forcing datasets, Meteoblue was selected as the primary source for 24, 48, and 72-hour predictions. This choice was informed by extensive validation against the 2010-2020 period, ensuring that the forcing data provides the necessary reliability for alpine meteorological conditions.

The operational architecture is built upon a three-module automated workflow—comprising data provider, modelling, and post-processing units—entirely coded in Python and deployed on Amazon Web Services (AWS) infrastructure. This cloud-based deployment enables continuous, automated daily model executions and displays results through a prototype dashboard. Following direct consultation with local stakeholders, the system was designed to communicate hazards at

a subbasin scale, identified as the most effective resolution for regional decision-making compared to basin-wide or pixel-based maps.

Figure 2: End-to-end execution flowchart of the prototype multi-hazard early warning system for the Upper Garonne River basin.

4.2.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

The flagship activity of DEM2 is the development and operationalization of a Prototype Multi-Hazard Early Warning System (MH-EWS) designed to address a critical gap of single-hazard frameworks: the lack of capacity to capture complex alpine interactions. In this region, heavy precipitation and snowmelt dynamics often trigger valley flooding and slope destabilization simultaneously. By moving beyond single hazard assessments, the DEM2 framework represents a paradigm shift, delivering concurrent flood and landslide forecasts at a subbasin scale. This integrated intelligence is provided across three distinct lead times and disseminated through an accessible web-based platform and mobile application, ensuring that emergency responses are based on the actual, multifaceted manifestation of mountain hazards.

The innovation of the system lies in its transition from a theoretical research prototype to a high-reliability operational service. Unlike many coupled models that require manual oversight, the MH-EWS implements full automation, covering the entire pipeline from data ingestion and weather forcing to hazard classification and warning dissemination. Deployed on cloud infrastructure, this automation enables daily, continuous forecasting that emergency managers can rely upon for real-time situational awareness. Furthermore, the system’s spatial resolution is the result of iterative stakeholder engagement, which determined that a subbasin-level approach best aligns with local jurisdictional boundaries and provides actionable detail without overwhelming decision-makers.

4.2.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

The MH-EWS is instrumental in strengthening the Nexus by connecting scientific innovation with operational risk reduction. It serves as the functional intersection of the project's various dimensions: the advanced modelling provides the forecasting engine, the operational framework

translates these results into warnings, and the data portal ensures information accessibility for both authorities and communities. This integration transforms scientific knowledge into tangible resilience, fostering evidence-based preparedness and the development of emergency protocols. By anticipating changing hazard patterns under climate variability, the system also establishes the necessary infrastructure for long-term climate adaptation, significantly enhancing the region's response to evolving environmental threats.

The MH-EWS demonstrates significant potential for replication across other mountain regions, particularly those characterized by snow-dominated hydrology and landslide susceptibility. This scalability is supported by a modular architecture that relies on open-source hydrological models and freely available weather forcing data, effectively reducing technical barriers to adoption. The use of cloud-based infrastructure further ensures computational scalability, allowing the system to handle multiple geographical regions simultaneously. However, successful transferability is contingent upon substantial upfront investment in region-specific model calibration. Precise landslide and flood forecasting require high-quality local data—including soil properties, detailed topography, and historical landslide inventories—which may not be readily available in all contexts. Furthermore, while scaling up to larger regions introduces complexities related to spatial heterogeneity and parameterization, scaling down to smaller catchments can be limited by the effective resolution of available weather forecasts and a lack of sufficient calibration data.

Reflecting on the development process, the modelling approach could be significantly enhanced by incorporating probabilistic forecasting and explicit uncertainty quantification. Integrating these elements from the outset would provide decision-makers with a more reliable understanding of risk, particularly for longer lead times. A primary area for future improvement is the integration of dynamic exposure data to transition the system from hazard forecasting to comprehensive risk analysis. By coupling the existing hazard models with spatial data on infrastructure, buildings, and population, the system could generate quantitative damage estimates and cost-benefit analyses. Such a development would not only refine the technical output but also strengthen the business case for preparedness investments by providing a clearer picture of potential socio-economic impacts. Finally, the long-term reliability of the model would benefit from more formalized feedback mechanisms with emergency responders. Establishing a systematic cycle to capture lessons learned from actual events would allow for continuous model refinement and calibration.

4.2.4. Take-home messages

The primary achievement of DEM2 is the successful translation of scientific innovation into a functional operational system. By utilizing the peer-reviewed SCLAM modelling framework, the project has demonstrated that integrated flood and landslide forecasting is an achievable operational capability, provided that coupled models are supported by cloud-based automation and stakeholder-informed design. This system now delivers continuous forecasts across multiple lead times, proving that technically sophisticated models can be effectively bridged with practical utility when spatial resolutions are tailored to match emergency response needs.

The project further reveals that while technical excellence is foundational, it is not sufficient on its own to ensure long-term resilience. The transition from a research prototype to a trusted operational system requires sustained stakeholder engagement, institutional capacity building, and early integration with national agencies. Moving forward, the effectiveness of such systems would be significantly enhanced by incorporating probabilistic uncertainty estimates and dynamic exposure data to provide quantitative risk assessments. Finally, DEM2 establishes a replicable template for mountain regions worldwide, highlighting that the true value of multi-hazard modelling lies in its ability to provide actionable, evidence-based intelligence for real-world disaster risk management.

4.3. DEM3 Lattari Mountains [Italy]

4.3.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

The DEM3 pilot case focuses on the Monti Lattari area, located in the southern part of the Campania Region, southern Italy. The area encompasses territories of outstanding naturalistic and historical-architectural value, including Sorrento and Amalfi, which attract large numbers of tourists from around the world. At the same time, the area is widely recognized as highly vulnerable to hydrogeological hazards of meteorological origin, primarily due to its distinctive geomorphological characteristics. A large portion of the hillslopes in the area are mantled by pyroclastic deposits resulting from past eruptions of the Somma-Vesuvius and Campi Flegrei volcanic complexes. The actual stratigraphy is therefore a function of successive eruptive events, which produced layers of ash and pumice of varying thickness. These materials, owing to their high water retention capacity and mineralogical composition, have made the area exceptionally fertile; however, they are also widely susceptible to shallow landslide initiation and debris flow triggering. In recent decades, such phenomena have caused substantial damage and loss of life. Among the most catastrophic events in Italy's recent history, the May 1998 disaster in Sarno involved geologically analogous terrains and stands as a benchmark reference for this type of hazard. Similarly, the geographical setting and the presence of small mountain catchments make the area prone to flash flooding and convective rainfall events.

To provide context for the modelling activities, it is useful to briefly describe the current operational early warning framework in place for the study area. The predictive system supporting the regional early warning system is currently based on the exceedance of rainfall threshold values associated with given return periods. Reference durations are defined as a function of catchment concentration time — with one hour adopted for urban catchments — while 24-, 48-, and 72-hour accumulations serve as the primary reference intervals. For each municipality, two or more rain gauges considered representative of the local rainfall regime are used as input. Return periods of 2, 5, and 10 years correspond respectively to alert, pre-alarm, and full alarm phases. This constitutes the operational, event-time component of the warning system. It is complemented by a preceding predictive phase in which a color-coded scheme (yellow, orange, and red) is assigned to broad macro-areas for different hydrogeological hazard typologies.

A fundamental limitation of this operational framework is that threshold exceedance is not directly linked to hazard triggering mechanisms, but rests on the implicit assumption that the rarer the rainfall event, the more likely the occurrence of a hydrogeological phenomenon. Antecedent soil moisture conditions are entirely disregarded, both to preserve the simplicity of the system and because no soil water content measurements are available from the official monitoring network — a gap that the monitoring activities at Amalfi and Sorrento have explicitly sought to address.

Against this backdrop, the modelling activities conducted on the pilot area have pursued two main objectives. The first is to assign physical meaning to the existing thresholds: specifically, to identify which combinations of pyroclastic cover thickness and lower boundary conditions are most critical, and to understand which configurations are brought to failure conditions when the rainfall accumulations currently used in the warning system are reached. The second objective is to assess the value added by incorporating antecedent soil moisture information into the warning framework. Since instrument-based monitoring at large spatial scales is not feasible, a key question addressed is whether reanalysis products and Earth Observation datasets can effectively substitute for point measurements, providing spatially distributed proxies for catchment wetness state. Both lines of work have been developed for the study area and have resulted in scientific contributions either already published or currently under peer review.

Figure 3: Framework developed for assessing and redefining rainfall thresholds.

Furthermore, a localized exposure model has been created in the entire Campania region, based on the Global Dynamic Exposure (GDE) model (that is described in detail as the main activity of DEM5, section 4.5). As the exposure was focused on landslides, it was not limited to building information (population, replacement costs) but also included length of street network types (footpath; cycle path; residential road; secondary road; primary road). We have focused on the exposure based on the GDE in the high-risk landslide areas and compared this with (population) exposure according to the census data. A review of the local data also identified and corrected local misclassifications in the global model, such as greenhouses around the airport of Salerno that were not classified as such in OpenStreetMap. We updated the model by including the Global Human Settlement Layer residential / non-residential distinction that is now used globally. This highlights the advantages of localized approaches to global exposure.

4.3.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

The modelling activities conducted on the pilot area developed along two main and complementary directions.

The first line of work aimed at translating the rainfall threshold values currently adopted in the Campania Region early warning system into physically meaningful terms. Empirical thresholds

used in territorial landslide early warning systems (Te-LEWS) are typically derived from statistical analyses of precipitation records and carry no direct physical correlation with infiltration dynamics and soil behavior. Physically based modelling approaches, on the other hand, have so far remained confined to local scale applications due to their high demand for spatially distributed geotechnical and hydrological parameters and their computational cost. The work developed an original framework that integrates geotechnical modelling with data-driven analysis, treating empirical and physically based approaches as synergic rather than alternative, with the objective of both interpreting existing thresholds and defining new ones grounded in the actual physical processes governing slope stability. The procedure is structured into four modules — geotechnical modelling, equalization time matrix generation, threshold interpretation, and threshold definition — and was developed and tested for the Campania Region, although it is designed to be transferable to other territorial warning systems employing empirical rainfall thresholds.

The second line of work addressed the role of antecedent wetness conditions, which are currently entirely absent from the Campania Region early warning system, contributing to a significant number of both false alarms and missed warnings. This work explored the use of the Soil Water Index (SWI) derived from the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) and the Global Flood Awareness System (GLOFAS) as a spatially distributed proxy for antecedent slope conditions. A prerequisite for this analysis was the construction of a landslide inventory for the Amalfi Coast, assembled by integrating eight existing catalogues and explicitly accounting for the spatial and temporal uncertainties embedded in the records. Results show that incorporating an SWI based attention threshold alongside the existing rainfall thresholds leads to a substantial reduction in both false alarms and missed warnings, demonstrating the potential of large-scale reanalysis products to complement and improve operational early warning in data scarce environments.

The relevance of these two lines of modelling work is grounded in both scientific and operational considerations. On one hand, translating the physical meaning of the existing warning thresholds moves the system beyond a purely statistical interpretation, making it possible to identify which slope configurations and soil conditions are genuinely at risk of failure when alert levels are reached. This significantly increases the credibility of the warning system and therefore the likelihood that local decision makers can use it in a conscious and informed manner, rather than responding to thresholds whose physical underpinning remains opaque. On the other hand, the integration of freely available soil water content data from reanalysis products provides a spatially distributed means of characterizing antecedent predisposing conditions, with the potential to substantially reduce false alarms and improve warning reliability. A key aspect of this approach is its accessibility: the datasets employed—EFAS at approximately 1.5 km resolution for Europe and its global counterpart GLOFAS at approximately 5 km resolution—are freely available for civil protection purposes. This makes the framework fully replicable across the entire European domain and, through GLOFAS, scalable to global coverage, representing a concrete pathway toward transferring the methodology developed on the Monti Lattari pilot case to other territorial early warning systems worldwide.

A further element of relevance is the low barrier to implementation. The findings from both modelling lines can be incorporated into the existing civil protection framework without requiring fundamental restructuring of current operational procedures, making the transition toward a more physically informed and antecedent-aware warning system practically achievable in the short term. At the same time, soil water content data—whether derived from reanalysis products, Earth Observation datasets, or in situ measurements—represent a natural candidate input for the operational platform developed within WP1, creating a direct and coherent link between the modelling outputs produced in the pilot case and the broader decision support infrastructure released at the project level.

4.3.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

Both modelling approaches are inherently scalable beyond the boundaries of the DEM3 pilot case. The physical interpretation framework for rainfall thresholds can, by its very nature, be extended to the entire territory currently covered by the Campania Region early warning system, ensuring replicability at the regional scale without methodological adaptation. Similarly, since EFAS soil water content data are available across the full European domain, the antecedent conditions approach can be applied wherever an assessment of predisposing wetness state is relevant to hydrogeological hazard warning, making the methodology transferable to any territorial early warning system operating within Europe that relies on rainfall thresholds and would benefit from an additional soil moisture based discriminator.

However, a careful balance must be maintained between increasing system complexity and preserving its operational manageability for decision makers. Within this trade-off, a promising direction for further development consists of enriching the soil moisture information base by incorporating additional sources, such as Earth Observation derived surface soil moisture estimates opportunely assimilated along the soil profile. This would allow a more robust characterization of uncertainty in antecedent conditions while keeping the overall framework operationally viable. In parallel, and consistent with the approach adopted throughout the monitoring and modelling activities, strengthening the dialogue with stakeholders remains a priority, not only at the municipal scale, where engagement has already proven productive, but also at the regional level, where institutional buy-in would be essential to translate the methodological advances achieved within the project into lasting improvements to the operational early warning system.

4.3.4. Take-home messages

The modelling activities conducted in the DEM3 Monti Lattari pilot case addressed a concrete operational gap in the Campania Region's landslide early warning system: the absence of any physically grounded or antecedent-condition-aware component. Two complementary lines of work were developed and validated.

The first provides a framework to translate existing empirical rainfall thresholds into physically meaningful terms, identifying which slope configurations and pyroclastic soil profiles are genuinely at risk of failure when alert levels are reached. This moves the warning system beyond a purely statistical interpretation and increases its credibility for local decision makers. The second line demonstrates that the Soil Water Index derived from EFAS — a freely available, operational reanalysis product — can serve as an effective proxy for antecedent wetness conditions, substantially reducing both false alarms and missed warnings when combined with the existing rainfall thresholds.

Both approaches are characterized by a low implementation barrier: they can be integrated into the current civil protection framework without requiring fundamental restructuring of operational procedures. Crucially, their replicability extends well beyond the pilot area. The physical threshold interpretation framework can be applied across the entire Campania Region warning system, while the EFAS-based antecedent conditions approach is transferable to any territorial early warning system operating within Europe and at global scale using GLOFAS. Soil water content data also represent a natural input candidate for the WP1 operational platform. The main recommendation for future development is to enrich the soil moisture information base through the assimilation of Earth Observation surface estimates along the soil profile, and to strengthen engagement with regional-level institutions to consolidate the pathway from research outputs to operational uptake.

4.4. DEM4 Vilnius [Lithuania]

The Vilnius Demonstrator (DEM4) did not commit to active modelling activities within the Task 4.3. However, some numerical modelling results of rainfall nowcasting and short-term forecasting were nevertheless used, in combination with expert assessment, to address the impact of rainfall on the stormwater drainage system of the city of Vilnius. The performed analyses were utilized as examples to start preliminary discussion with the municipality on potential useful revisions of planning strategies. In particular, a preliminary analysis of the rainwater systems' drainage area in the old part of the Vilnius historic centre (UNESCO World heritage site) was used to demonstrate that the impact of different rainfall scenarios can be assessed and the adequacy of the drainage system in the context of a changing climate can be evaluated.

4.5. DEM5 Schleswig-Holstein State [Germany]

4.5.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

The modelling activities for DEM5 focus on the advancement of the Global Dynamic Exposure (GDE) model. This model has been developed within the HuT, building upon previous research initially funded by the LEXIS and RISE project (EU). This included a complete rewrite of the software core and a new database design to allow the model to capture varying datasets per building to allow for different properties stored per building. This accounts for the varying availability of data across different regions or countries. To be able to provide the most permissive license possible and to make the entire process more transparent, we have also developed a new set of country exposure models (the Open Exposure Model, OXM) which describe the overall distribution of structural types of buildings in the country. We use these model as input to specify for each building the possible distribution of types (in a probabilistic way considering all known building properties).

The model now describes approximately 2.7 billion buildings globally and can be considered complete in most countries (notable exceptions are China, South Korea and Taiwan, where no open building dataset exists besides OSM). The model combines global data from OSM, Google Open Buildings, Microsoft ML Footprints, EUBucco, the Global Human Settlement Layer, and PAGER country exposure data. In incomplete areas, the built area from the Global Human Settlement Layer is used to approximate the number of buildings. For each building, we provide the building footprint and in most cases the building height, which in turn is used to estimate the number of stories and the floor space inside the building. For some areas in Europe, we have introduced full 3D building geometries. Each footprint is accompanied with a probability distribution of different structural types that can be related to the vulnerability of the building. Further attributes that we provide are the occupancy (covering a list of around 100 different types of building usage), estimated construction year, number of people inside the building during daytime, nighttime and transit time as well as the structural value and for some countries the non-structural value and content values. The population and value attributes are scaled to the usable floor space of each building. Attributes that we don't provide everywhere are number of dwellings per building and their average area as well as the total replacement costs. The latter will soon be included in OXM and then available on the building scale.

Due to its sheer size and processing needs, this model is fully algorithmic and driven by processing rules that are managed in a rule engine. The rules define the extraction and combination of building attributes from occupancy determination to selection of structural types.

We have looked into detail at the building exposure in Glückstadt. Here, we have created a detailed and up-to-date exposure map of the buildings in Glückstadt using Unmanned Airborne Vehicles (UAVs). We have mapped the Glückstadt area for one day, using the DJI Mini 4 Pro model with a normal camera. In total 450 buildings were mapped. The UAVs provided high-resolution and georeferenced images, that were transformed to accurate building footprints using photogrammetry techniques, using the Drone Tasking Manager, CloudCompare and Meshroom. From these we were able to create a 3D city model including roof geometries and accurate building footprints. From this we could measure attributes like building height, number of floors, and roof type, instead of estimating them through aggregated exposure models. The result of the dynamic exposure mapping was a complete and more reliable local dataset that can be used for risk assessment or to assess damages after a disaster. The results are shared at the European Geoscience Union 2026 (Rao et al., 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu26-21400>) and the point cloud as well as the 3D model can be found on Zenodo under an open data license (10.5281/zenodo.19481586).

Figure 4: The 3D model generated for Glückstadt, with the number of stories as found in OpenStreetMap.

4.5.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

Many hazards are very location-specific and demand building and population data at the same level of granularity for reasonable risk assessments that can inform any type of mitigation measures. GDE provides this level of information in a free, open and collaborative way. Risk or impact analyses of highly localized hazards like flash floods can now be performed without extra local data capture or relying on large scale exposure models that don't describe the exact location of assets.

By combining the global model of the GDE with high-resolution mapping of Glückstadt, we create a global-to-local continuum: the GDE provides the global framework, where in the demonstrator area it is enriched locally. It opens doors to citizen-science activities, where areas that citizens find to be poorly mapped can be enriched by the citizens themselves. The OpenStreetMap information in Glückstadt was 5–6 years out of date. Building geometries have changed in the meantime due to renovations and new buildings are added. The UAV inquiry is a fast and effective

way of high-quality mapping of the area. On top of that, a 3D model has been created, making the area one of the most detailed in the GDE model. This has been used to deduce the number of stories and can later be used for more complex methods in flood risk assessment.

With the GDE, there are no licensing barriers and the data ownership shifts from institutions to citizens. As all information is open, the ownership of the data shifts from institutions to citizens. Anyone that is interested in the data can view and download it. Non-technical users can use OpenAerialMap and OpenStreetMap, researchers can also retrieve the point cloud and 3D building model. The updates to the GDE reduce uncertainties in the exposure model, further reducing uncertainties in flood risk models.

The scale of the GDE is global, covering every inhabited area of the world, which ensures immediate use in any region. However, its design allows local actors to move beyond the global baseline by introducing specific rules into the processing chain. By adding locally specific rules to the rule engine, one can refine the model to reflect regional differences in exposure.

4.5.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

Due to the shift of ownership from institutions to citizens, the GDE has a built-in self-correction method by constantly updating from the ever growing dataset of OSM (in size but also in detail). However, the produced data is difficult to validate due to a lack of ground truth. In general, wherever ground truth is available (e.g. cadastral building dataset), it is already part of the model. Then the model augments this data with further attributes from other sources.

The method developed specifically for Glückstadt has been seamlessly integrated into the GDE pipeline. It demonstrates that local augmentation of a global model is possible and feasible. However, such method requires relatively high effort for the coverage: in one day we were able to capture the city center (~450 buildings) using the UAV flights.

4.5.4. Take home messages

The GDE model is up and running and is producing global data releases every 6 months. This data provides the highest possible resolution for exposure models, i.e. on the building scale. Its openness allows for flexible use in many contexts of risk mitigation and disaster management, but also in city planning and climate change adaption. All-in-all, the local approach to exposure modelling could augment global models and reduce uncertainties in risk assessment. The Glückstadt Demonstrator Area demonstrates how local data collection can be beneficial for a global framework such as the GDE model. We were able to generate accurate building footprints, roof types, building heights, number of stories, and building volumes for around 450 buildings in the city centre using only open-source methods. A drone and technical expertise are not needed to improve exposure information. Citizens can also contribute through platforms such as OpenStreetMap or mobile applications like StreetComplete. Data ownership remains with the public rather than being restricted to private companies or governmental institutions. At the same time, more advanced outputs such as the orthophoto, point cloud, and 3D city model have been openly published, allowing both non-technical users and researchers to benefit from the results. This can give us better insights into risk assessment and post-disaster damage estimation than aggregated (outdated) datasets.

4.6. DEM6 East fjords [Iceland]

4.6.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

The modelling activities within DEM6 were designed to establish a framework for landslide early warning through the definition of site-specific quantitative thresholds. This work moved beyond generic regional models by focusing on the unique geological and geomorphological characteristics of the area, specifically addressing the hydrometeorological controls that trigger both shallow and deep-seated slope failures. By combining a high-resolution historical inventory of events dating back to 1990 with localized meteorological data, the team recalibrated intensity-duration (I-D) rainfall thresholds. This calibration accounted for the varying spatial representativity of the local rain-gauge network, ensuring that the resulting warning triggers reflect the actual physical conditions of the soil.

To address the complexity of deep-seated landslide processes, the framework was extended with subsurface data from twelve borehole water-level monitoring stations. To organize and interpret these time series, the team developed a conceptual hydrological "tank model" that aggregates the borehole observations into a weighted, dimensionless proxy for slope saturation and hydrological loading, with automatic tracking of baseline shifts and exceedance durations. Rather than diagnosing instability directly, this proxy surfaces long-term changes including a sustained rise in baseline saturation observed since the 2020 landslide that support expert interpretation of possible progressive change. Linking this internal saturation state explicitly to external weather forcing and to quantitative geotechnical stability remains the objective of the planned Factor of Safety model.

Furthermore, the analytical framework was expanded to include the long-term effect of moisture through the calculation of antecedent precipitation indices over a 10-year horizon. This approach captures the delayed hydrological response of the slope, identifying periods of increased vulnerability where the soil's "memory" of past rainfall significantly lowers the threshold for new failures. All these modelling components rainfall thresholds, groundwater saturation proxies, and antecedent moisture indices have been operationalised for near real-time visualization via Grafana. This integration enables automated detection and decision support, while the conceptual establishment of a Factor of Safety (FoS) stability model provides a clear pathway toward a fully automated, physics-based warning system in the near future.

4.6.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

The core innovation of this activity is the integration and harmonization of heterogeneous monitoring data into a unified operational framework. A key technical feature is the translation of raw borehole water-level observations into a dimensionless, normalized "fill level". This allows for a direct and intuitive comparison across different sensors and elevation zones, regardless of their specific local characteristics. By utilizing the conceptual tank model, the system provides a physically interpretable proxy for slope saturation and hydrological loading, making heterogeneous raw sensor data comparable across zones and supporting expert decision-making for emergency managers.

This framework is instrumental in strengthening the Environment–Risk–Society Nexus within the context of Seyðisfjörður, a town where the 2020 landslide disaster highlighted the urgent need for systematic early warning. On the environmental dimension, the activity integrates precipitation, antecedent moisture, and groundwater responses to provide a holistic view of the drivers behind both shallow and deep-seated landslides. The implementation within the Demonstrator was achieved by transitioning historical datasets—including landslide inventories and decadal

precipitation records—into a real-time visualization environment via Grafana. This platform automatically classifies data into predefined warning levels and tracks sustained critical conditions, such as threshold exceedances lasting more than 48 hours. While the system currently operates as an internal expert tool, it establishes a robust foundation for future public dissemination. Furthermore, the conceptual framework for a factor-of-safety slope-stability model has been established, providing a clear evolutionary pathway toward a fully automated, physics-based risk management system as the local data infrastructure continues to mature.

4.6.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

The methodology shows significant potential for transferability, primarily because it is designed to rely on widely available hydro-meteorological data. By utilizing conceptual modelling and threshold-based analysis instead of computationally intensive numerical simulations, the approach remains suitable for regions with limited technical or computational resources. Its implementation on the Grafana platform further enhances its replicability, allowing other authorities to integrate these tools into existing monitoring infrastructures with relative ease. However, the scalability of the system is fundamentally tied to data density; the reliability of the "tank model" and its associated thresholds depends on having a sufficient network of groundwater sensors and long-term historical records, making it less applicable in areas with sparse monitoring or significant data gaps.

While the framework is robust, several technical constraints inherent in its design must be acknowledged. The approach is deeply site-specific, meaning that threshold values and normalization parameters require localized calibration to reflect specific geological and climatic conditions; they cannot simply be "copy-pasted" from one slope to another. Furthermore, the tank model remains a conceptual simplification that focuses on saturation proxies rather than explicitly simulating the complex hydro-mechanical failure mechanisms of the soil. This underscores the need for expert interpretation, as the system currently operates as an informed decision-support tool rather than a fully autonomous predictive model.

Several adjustments could have further optimized the outcome. Earlier integration of the conceptual tank framework during the initial sensor network design would have improved the spatial representativity of the boreholes, ensuring more effective placement across different elevation zones. Additionally, incorporating deformation measurements, such as GNSS or total station data, directly into the threshold logic would have provided a more definitive link between hydrological loading and actual slope response. Looking forward, the integration of weather and hydrological forecasts represents the next critical evolution for the system. By transitioning from current precipitation triggers to forecast-based indicators, and potentially incorporating AI-driven analysis, the framework can move from near real-time monitoring toward a truly predictive early warning capability.

4.6.4. Take home messages

The main outcome of this activity is the successful transformation of scientific research into an operational framework, demonstrating that landslide early warning capabilities are most effectively strengthened through the integration of site-specific thresholds and modern data infrastructure. By developing distinct indicators for precipitation, antecedent moisture, and groundwater levels, the framework provides a comprehensive solution for both shallow and deep-seated slope instabilities. These methods have been operationalized within a Grafana-based environment, shifting from passive monitoring to a proactive system characterized by real-time visualization and automated warning levels.

A critical, often overlooked enabler of this success was the systemic restructuring of core databases. The migration of landslide and weather inventories to a PostgreSQL environment significantly enhanced data interoperability, allowing analytical models that were previously restricted to offline use to be integrated into live, continuous dashboards. This technical evolution ensures that indicators like precipitation return periods and groundwater "fill levels" are updated in real time, providing emergency managers with immediate situational awareness.

While the approach is highly replicable due to its computationally lightweight nature and reliance on standard hydro-meteorological data, the study also identifies clear pathways for future development. A significant challenge remains the explicit modelling of snowmelt and runoff, which are dominant triggers in the Icelandic climate but are currently only implicitly represented. Moving forward, the most impactful improvement will be the direct integration of numerical weather predictions and hydrological runoff models.

4.7. DEM7 Tisza River Basin [Hungary]

4.7.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

The flagship modelling activity of DEM7 focuses on mitigating municipal pluvial flood risks by leveraging an extensive monitoring network of precipitation, groundwater, and discharge data. The central innovation involves integrating real-time soil moisture as a dynamic input parameter, significantly enhancing the accuracy of runoff and infiltration capacity forecasts during extreme weather. This refined methodology is operationalized through the VÍZ24 mobile application, which translates complex hydrological preconditions into accessible, settlement-scale risk classifications. By providing up-to-date situational awareness, the system empowers local municipalities to manage localized flooding effectively, bridging the gap between sophisticated environmental monitoring and practical urban flood protection.

4.7.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

The core innovation of this activity is the transition to a multi-factor dynamic risk assessment that integrates traditional precipitation data with five critical parameters: inland water hazard maps, drainage infrastructure condition, receiving water body capacity, and official protection levels. The defining feature is the inclusion of real-time soil moisture status, which historical analysis of 24 events (2016–2024) proved to be a decisive indicator of flood occurrence. By moving beyond "precipitation-only" models, the system accurately captures the complex hydrological preconditions of the Great Hungarian Plain.

4.7.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

The methodology developed in the Middle Tisza region serves as a functional bridge to translate complex environmental data (soil saturation and meteorological warnings) into actionable risk classifications delivered via the VÍZ24 mobile application. This approach empowers municipal authorities—who often lack technical expertise—with real-time decision support, directly linking scientific innovation to local governance and societal resilience. Finally, the system transforms regional monitoring into a transparent, condition-based framework that enhances preparedness for the increasingly frequent extreme weather events driven by climate change.

The methodology is highly suited for amplification due to its transferable framework and reliance on data types—such as meteorological observations and soil moisture—that are increasingly becoming standard in modern water management. As a digital platform, the VÍZ24 mobile

application offers straightforward geographical scalability, allowing it to be adapted to other lowland regions facing similar pluvial flood challenges. Furthermore, the system serves as a tool for institutional capacity building, providing high-level technical assistance to local municipalities that often lack the specialized hydrological expertise required for sophisticated risk assessment.

However, successful replication is contingent upon overcoming several data-related challenges. The system is fundamentally dependent on the availability of continuous soil moisture monitoring, which may not be present in all regions. Additionally, the relatively short historical record of soil moisture data (dating back only to 2016) currently limits the statistical robustness of the model's validation. To improve the approach, future efforts should prioritize expanding the spatial density of monitoring networks and accumulating longer datasets to refine the model's predictive accuracy. Strengthening the evidence base through a broader range of case studies across diverse climatic conditions will be essential to further refine the system and ensure its long-term reliability as a standard for urban flood management.

4.7.4. Take home messages

The flagship activity demonstrates that effective pluvial flood risk management requires moving beyond rainfall-based approaches and incorporating antecedent environmental conditions, particularly soil moisture. The development of the VÍZ24 mobile application represents a practical and innovative solution that bridges the gap between scientific data and operational decision-making at the municipal level. By integrating real-time data, risk assessment methodologies, and early warning functions, it significantly enhances preparedness and response capacity. The findings clearly show that soil moisture is a key preconditioning factor in pluvial flood generation, especially in flatland regions. Incorporating this parameter enables more accurate and dynamic risk assessments, supporting proactive rather than reactive management.

Such solutions are essential for improving resilience to climate change and advancing sustainable water management within the Water–Climate–Risk Nexus.

4.8. DEM8 Ogliastra [Italy]

4.8.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

The modelling activities of DEM8 are designed to provide the scientific and knowledge-based foundation necessary for policy and decision-makers to define effective adaptation and mitigation strategies for wildfire prevention, focusing on both forest and wildland-urban interface fires. The work is structured into three integrated blocks, where high-resolution fire behavior modelling is used to simulate fire impacts under current and future climate conditions to assess adaptation strategies and Nature-based Solutions. To feed these simulations, researchers analyzed ERA5-land reanalysis data and six climate models across different scenarios (historical, SSP126, and SSP370), using the FlamMap software to generate spatial outputs such as burn probability, flame length, and crown fire fraction.

In addition, the project developed a prototype of an innovative insurance solution named "Fire Safe Community", which is a Community-Based Catastrophe Insurance (CBCI) product. This prototype validates the use of transparent, localized risk models for pricing coverage and explores the possibility of linking insurance premiums to community-implemented mitigation actions. These technical activities were closely integrated with participatory workshops and focus groups to ensure that the modelling process was informed by local stakeholder knowledge and governance perspectives.

Figure 5: Flowchart of the proposed approach

4.8.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

The primary innovation of this study lies in its ability to bridge scientific modelling with stakeholder dialogue through a participatory approach that draws on geography, sociology, and anthropology. This interdisciplinary integration ensures that the developed fire risk solutions are grounded in real-world needs and are both acceptable to stakeholders and feasible for implementation. The process led to the co-design of three specific land management scenarios: "WUI & Roads", focusing on treatments around infrastructure; "Fire-Smart forest management", involving preventive silviculture; and "Mosaic Landscape management", which integrates agropastoral and agroforestry activities. The insurance prototype further innovates by moving beyond traditional indemnity insurance to act as a proactive governance and mitigation tool that can help close the insurance protection gap. This activity is instrumental to improve the Environment–Risk–Society Nexus as it explicitly links climate, ecosystems, land management, and socio-economic dimensions within a single integrated framework. By combining fire behavior simulations with stakeholder knowledge and governance structures, the approach enables a systemic understanding of wildfire risk and supports coordinated strategies across sectors such as forestry, agriculture, and urban planning.

4.8.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

The approach offers high potential for replication in other contexts because it combines widely available climate data, established fire modelling tools, and participatory methods. It is particularly suitable for local-scale applications where stakeholder engagement helps tailor solutions to specific socio-ecological contexts, thereby increasing their effectiveness. The insurance prototype serves as a proof of concept that can be replicated in other regions with similar datasets, fostering partnerships between insurance providers and disaster risk reduction stakeholders.

However, the process is highly demanding in terms of time, data, and expertise, which can be a barrier where technical capacity or stakeholder networks are limited. While technical models can

be scaled up, meaningful stakeholder engagement becomes harder to replicate at larger scales without losing depth and inclusiveness.

Future improvements could involve a deeper integration between the insurance solution and the modelling process, which has only been partially explored thus far. Furthermore, a more in-depth market analysis and the integration of wildfire coverage into multi-peril policies encompassing other risks like floods or landslides would strengthen the approach and its practical applicability.

4.8.4. Take home messages

This flagship activity demonstrates that an integrated approach combining climate-driven fire modelling with stakeholder knowledge is effective for bridging the gap between science and practice in fire risk management. By linking high-resolution simulations with participatory co-design, the project enabled the testing of land management scenarios that are both technically sound and locally accepted. The "Fire Safe Community" prototype provides a proof of concept for how innovations in the insurance sector can create opportunities for better risk management by linking premiums to mitigation actions through catastrophe modelling. Ultimately, the experience in Ogliastra highlights that systemic resilience to wildfires requires a holistic framework that integrates geospatial data, weather-climatic information, and stakeholder-driven governance to produce actionable recommendations for policy and practice.

4.9. DEM 9 Dorset County [UK]

4.9.1. Introduction on the activities carried out on modelling

Modelling activities within DEM9 have centred on four broad themes linked to the aim of DEM 9 and supporting stakeholder understanding: advancing impact-based forecasting methodologies, strengthening cross-organisational collaboration, developing hazard-specific modelling capabilities, and expanding user-focused and data-driven approaches.

4.9.2. Main features and the link with the Nexus

Through the activities of the Met Office, work has progressed on improving how hazard, exposure, and vulnerability information is integrated into impact-based warning systems. This includes completing comparative modelling experiments using RiskScape, drafting and submitting academic papers on methodological choices in IBFW, and building international collaboration with New Zealand partners on vulnerability and exposure analysis for major storm events. Presentations and workshops have helped communicate these advances and align them with multi-risk forecasting ambitions. This work is complemented by a new collaborative paper submitted to *Weather, Climate and Society*, examining how methodological choices in exposure and vulnerability integration influence warning outcomes.

Met Office modelling teams have also engaged in broader hazard-related research in the UK, including participation in workshops on monthly-to-seasonal hazard prediction aimed at improving modelling, post-processing, and decision-support strategies across time horizon. Within DEM 9 a significant focus has been on building partnerships across the Met Office, BGS, the UK Natural Hazard Partnership. Joint workshops and meetings have supported knowledge exchange on landslide forecasting, feature-based clustering of ensemble forecasts, and cross-organisational workflows. Engagement with the UK Cabinet Office has also helped clarify data needs and decision-support requirements in the UK for socio-economic impact data, a complex need and a key focus of IBF.

Knowledge exchange on modelling work has supported cross agency working across hazard domains. Progress has been made in landslide-related modelling through the BGS–Met Office collaboration. Several collaboration meetings have advanced joint work on landslide forecasting, visualisation, feature-based clustering, and cross-organisational workflows.

Work has also expanded into climate-timescale hazard modelling for heat and wildfire risk in Dorset. Building on earlier Ensemble Prediction System First Guess Warning (EPS-W; <https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/met.1377>) heat hazard analysis, the team established new partnerships with organisations such as the RNLI, National Trust, and RLSS UK to understand operational needs and access relevant datasets, including beach-attendance records and NHS Hospital Episode Statistics. This has enabled exploration of links between heat events and water-related emergencies, alongside early engagement on future wildfire risk modelling using UKCP RCM data.

4.9.3. The HuT amplification and how to improve the approach

The HuT project has further highlighted the value of bringing together hazard modelling, exposure–vulnerability analysis, and operational user insight, but its impact could be amplified by strengthening integration across these strands. Presentation of a clear end-to-end workflow—from data acquisition and model development through to visualisation, communication, and operational testing—would help ensure that modelling outputs in this space are both technically robust and directly usable by decision-makers.

Expanding cross-organisational collaboration, particularly between the Met Office, BGS, and emergency response partners, has supported more consistent approaches to communications. Whilst there is a lot of work still to do on landslide thresholds, clustering methods, and multi-hazard scenario assessment there is a clear focus for this continuing.

Finally, embedding user-needs analysis earlier in the modelling cycle, improving access to socio-economic impact datasets, and developing more intuitive visual products would enhance the HuT’s ability to translate complex modelling into actionable, impact-focused guidance.

4.9.4. Take home messages

Collectively, these activities demonstrate strong progress in developing, testing, and operationalising modelling approaches under The HuT Nexus project. These are building to integrate hazard, exposure, and vulnerability information to support more effective impact-based forecasting and multi-hazard decision-making.

4.10. DEM10 Berne Canton [Switzerland]

The Berne Canton Demonstrator (DEM10) did not commit to active modelling activities within the Task 4.3. The DEM focused, within WP4, entirely on the design and establishment of a monitoring network. These activities, which represent the core scientific and innovation contributions of DEM10, are documented in full in the companion Deliverable D4.4.

5. Conclusions

The modelling activities documented in this Deliverable reflect the breadth and diversity of approaches that the ten Demonstrators of The HuT project have adopted to transform raw environmental data into operational and decision-making knowledge. Collectively, they constitute a rich portfolio ranging from the physical simulation of hazards to the modelling of dynamic exposure and socio-economic vulnerability, all unified by the Nexus philosophy: modelling is not a theoretical exercise but a decision-support tool that acquires value only when integrated into governance processes and community response.

The most represented modelling approach is the integration of hydrological and slope stability systems for the prediction of geo-hydrological risks. In the demonstrators of Val d'Aran (DEM2), the Lattari Mountains (DEM3), the Icelandic Fjords (DEM6), and the Tisza Basin (DEM7), physical and conceptual models have been refined to overcome the limitations of traditional single-hazard frameworks. In this context, soil moisture and antecedent hydrological conditions have emerged as fundamental cross-cutting variables. Their role as a preconditioning factor for instability has been recognized as a key element for reducing false alarms and improving the accuracy of forecasts for both shallow and deep-seated landslides and pluvial flooding. An activity functional to global-scale risk assessment is the Global Dynamic Exposure (GDE) model developed in DEM5. This activity has demonstrated how rule-driven algorithmic modelling can transform open data, such as OpenStreetMap, into a dynamic exposure framework covering 2.7 billion buildings. The capacity of this model to integrate 3D geometries, probabilistic structural types, and dynamic demographic data provides an unprecedented basis for high-precision impact analysis, removing barriers related to licensing and data acquisition costs. The experience of DEM8 has added an innovative socio-economic dimension by linking the physical modelling of wildfires with the co-design of land management scenarios and insurance prototypes. The "Fire Safe Community" model represents a tangible proof of how catastrophe modelling can be used to incentivize prevention, linking the reduction of insurance premiums to mitigation actions implemented by the community.

Not all DEMs were expected to carry out activities within the scope of this task. The portfolio of modelling innovations across the project reflects a strategic allocation of efforts, specifically calibrated to local technical baselines, the complexity of local hazard-risk interactions, as well as the specific requirements for decision support and the real socioeconomic conditions of each area. Where new modelling frameworks were not developed or refined, the decision was driven by these localized needs; in such cases, the complementary contributions in terms of monitoring and governance of those Demonstrators are valorized and documented in the relevant deliverables.

Several cross-cutting lessons emerge from the collective experience: spatial and temporal resolution is decisive; institutional integration is essential; the success of the transition toward operational systems depends on the involvement of stakeholders from the earliest stages of development; technical barriers remain significant: the need for specific local calibrations and the dependence on the density of monitoring networks represent challenges for the universal scalability of the models. Looking ahead, the challenge for the final phase of the project is to ensure that the modelling innovations developed are amplified and formally integrated into the operational systems for disaster risk reduction that will persist after the project concludes. The foundation for this amplification has been laid: the frameworks have been validated, and the linkages between environmental observations, hazard interpretation, and risk management have been significantly strengthened within the Nexus.

